

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND ANALYTICAL REVIEWS (IJRAR)

An International Open Access Journal | Approved By ISSN and UGC

Ref No : IJRAR/Vol 5 / Issue 4/ 089

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About IJRAR : UGC and ISSN Approved - International Peer Reviewed Journal, Refereed Journal, Indexed Journal, Impact Factor: 5.75, E-ISSN 2348-1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138

Registration ID : IJRAR_193750

Paper ID : IJRAR1905089

Title of Paper : DIGITAL MARKETING INDUSTRY IN INDIA: CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATIONS

Impact Factor : 5.75 (Calculate by Google Scholar) | License by Creative Common 3.0

DOI :

Published in : Volume 5 | Issue 4 | December 2018

Page No : 468-476

Published URL : http://www.ijrar.org/viewfull.php?&p_id=IJRAR1905089

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International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews - IJRAR
(E-ISSN 2348-1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138)

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Website: www.ijrar.org | Email: editor@ijrar.org

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND
ANALYTICAL REVIEWS (IJRAR) | E-ISSN 2348-1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138**
An International Open Access Journal

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DIGITAL MARKETING INDUSTRY IN INDIA: CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATIONS

Published In IJRAR (www.ijrar.org) ISSN UGC Approved & 5.75 Impact Factor

Volume 5 Issue 4 December 2018

PAPER ID : IJRAR1905089

Registration ID : 193750

R.B. Joshi
EDITOR IN CHIEF

UGC and ISSN Approved - International Peer Reviewed Journal, Refereed Journal, Indexed Journal, Impact Factor: 5.75 Google Scholar

Website: www.ijrar.org | Email id: editor@ijrar.org | ESTD: 2014

DIGITAL MARKETING INDUSTRY IN INDIA: CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract: The digital marketing industry is seeing an exponential rise in India. With the entry of e-Commerce players like Snapdeal and Flipkart, the digital marketing arena started to pick. Technology is helping marketers to strategize and measure more effectively. It is also helping in making the digital marketing operations smoother and more productive. The technology is helping the marketers to segment their audience on the basis of their demographics, behaviour, and preferences. At the same time buying behaviour has drastically changed over the past decade, and now more consumers are starting (and often ending) their buyer's journey online, virtually showing the effectiveness of how digital marketing works. This shift in the way that consumers make purchasing decisions and buy products and services have made digital marketing a must for any business that's trying to compete in the modern marketplace, regardless of size or industry. It's important for business owners to understand how digital marketing works so that they can strategically use the right digital tools and campaign tactics to reach and engage their audience. Digital marketing is a way to promote brands and products online and through other digital channels. There are a number of different digital technologies that marketers and companies use to get their marketing message to their target audience. This paper analyzes the concept of digital marketing in India and also emphasize on the challenges and implications of digital marketing.

Keywords: E-marketing, content marketing, social media, online advertisements, technology, customer service

Introduction

Digital marketing has a huge potential in India as it is a hugely populated country and studies show that an average Indian spends 4.4 hours in a day on the internet while using their laptops. The smart phone penetration in the country is also on the rise and using their smart devices they spend nearly 3.1 hours on an average on the internet. A study revealed that, the Indian internet traffic will be nearly 291 times more than what it was in 2005. The huge revolution in the digital operations has opened doors for digital marketing in the country. The market for digital marketing is huge given that 68% of the brands selling in the percentage are only going to increase in the future. Out of this 68%, 42% of the brands today are opting for social media marketing as their prime digital marketing platform. This is because all those internet users who are still not inclined to buy things online are present on some social platform, especially Facebook and Twitter. By using these social platforms, the companies make sure that they are able to reach out to these people. They then hope to bring these people to their websites through their different marketing strategies.

Digital Marketing is in booming stage and a lot of start-up companies are depending on it not only in India but all over the world. The purpose of digital marketing campaigns is to make the sales and to create brand awareness among the audience. The main objective is to reduce the cost of advertising and increase return on investment. In simple terms, digital marketing can be defined as the advertisements and promotions carried out through the internet. Digital marketing is in fact, an umbrella term comprising of several other divisions such as content marketing, email marketing, Pay Per Click (PPC), Pay Per View (PPV), Online Reputation Management, Social Media Marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Mobile Marketing etc. to name a few. The increasing popularity of internet is enabling several newer forms of marketing arenas in the digital space. In the year 2017, India ranked No. 1 in the list of nations worldwide in terms of mobile data usage. All the businesses are intending to go digital because of its various advantages. The growing rate of internet users has made it clear that digital marketing is reckoned to be the future of marketing.

According to a report by Adsyndicate, the Indian economy has been on one of the brightest spots globally with GDP growth of 6.4% in 2017. The economy is expected to fully shelve the demonetization and GST impact and achieve growth rate of 7.5% in 2018. The economy is on a roll and the investment in digital stack especially Aadhaar and Aadhaar-enabled services is going to further fuel the economy with ease in

credit access, availing government services and is poised to become a \$6 Tn GDP by 2027. The digital advertising revenues for the year 2017 in India has reached INR10,150 crores and is further expected to grow at a CAGR of 30% to reach INR 29,450 crores by 2021. As the digital ecosystem continues to develop with low-cost smart phones and access of high-speed data connection, digital content consumption is likely to become more frequent and more mainstream. The data consumption has grown multi-fold over the last few years largely fueled by Reliance Jio which brought low cost data plans in the marketplace. Today, Jio is the world's largest data network operator carrying over 16,000 TB of data on its network with over 13.8 crores users across the length and breadth of the country. Furthermore, the launch of OTT by Netflix, Hotstar, Voot and existing behemoth Youtube and Facebook has only helped push the envelope further in terms of per user data consumption which today stands at 3.9GB/Month.

In the future, we will witness AI making an impact in areas such as digital marketing and content marketing. On the other side, chatbots will go mainstream and moving out of its cocoon wherein brands will not only look for a vendor but a partner who can deliver both automated as well as human intervention for delivering good customer experience.

Source: Morgan Stanley, FICCI KPMG M&E Report, 2017, Economicstimes.indiatimes.com, Telecom.economicstimes.indiatimes.com

Key Digital Marketing Trends:

Website marketing

The company's website plays a vital role in how digital marketing works and it is the cornerstone of the digital marketing strategy. This is where many of the target customers first get an impression of the brand, and then the leads will eventually convert into paying customers. The goal of digital marketing is to attract, engage, and convert the leads. The website is sometimes the brand's only chance to make a good first impression with consumers in the target market. For this reason, one should pay attention to the layout of the site as well as the colours and graphics that is used in the site design. If the content or layout of the website is unattractive then people will stop engaging with a website.

Web advertising is a form of marketing and advertising which uses the Internet to deliver promotional marketing messages to an audience. It includes many different formats and contains items such as text, images, flash, video, and audio. The main purpose of web advertising is to deliver general advertisements and brand messages to site visitors.

Search Engine Optimization

Search engine optimization also plays a big role in how digital marketing works. Search engine optimization is the process of optimizing the site's content so that it appeals to the search engines. The ultimate goal is to rank higher on the search engine results page (SERP) to increase visibility in the target market. The higher is the rank on the SERP, the more organic traffic can drive back to the website.

Search engine optimization not only brings more traffic to the website, but it also helps ensure that the leads brought are of a higher quality. The goal of digital marketing is to attract the right customers for the products or services, and SEO plays an important role in doing that. The marketers should emphasize on certain keywords and topics within the content of the website, so that they can attract the customers who are most likely to be interested in their products or services.

A recent research study by Forrester found that 71% of consumers start their buyer's journey on search engines like Google. If marketers are not taking the right steps to improve the site's SEO then they may be missing out on a powerful opportunity to reach a significant amount of leads. Every individual uses search engines to get any information about a service, product or brand online. SEO consists of a number of activities such as linkable assets creation, keyword analysis, organic link building, title tag, Meta tag etc.

Social Media Marketing

Most of the brands today are using social media marketing to support their digital marketing campaigns and drive more traffic to their website. Social media marketing involves promoting the content and engaging with the target consumers on social media channels like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Pinterest. Social media is definitely one of the most important things to happen in the digital arena that business owners and digital marketers can leverage on to create brand awareness for their products and services. Through Social Media Marketing (SMM), digital marketers can reach out to highly target and specific customers through direct and person-to-person engagement. One of the biggest appeals of social media marketing is that it allows businesses to reach a wider audience online.

According to a report by Lyfemarketing (2018), 79% of American internet users are active on Facebook. If the business is not trying to reach and engage these consumers on the social platform, then they are certainly missing out on an important opportunity to reach new leads. This is a platform used to promote a product or service. Most social media platforms have built-in data analytics tools, which enable companies to track the progress, success, and engagement of ad campaigns.

Social media not only favoured its users to interact with others on a global scale, but also opened doors for several marketers to promote their products. Thus, marketing domain has risen to new horizons of 'social media marketing', which focused on marketing exclusively on the social media platforms. The popularity of social media marketing is increasing since it has a lot of advantages over traditional marketing. For example, it has larger target audience coverage, allows for customer feedback, builds brand loyalty effectively and is highly economical compared to traditional marketing. However, the competition for social media marketing is also increasing with massive number of social media agencies emerging with innovative techniques.

PPC Advertising

PPC (pay-per-click) ads are a type of advertising that involves paying the ad publisher every time a new lead clicks on the ad. These ads are useful for targeting clients within a short period of time. Choosing proper keywords and contextual as well as visual information in ads are factors that decide the effectiveness of PPC ads. Google AdWords is one of the most popular and effective types of PPC ads. Google AdWords helps the businesses to appear on the first page of the search engine results.

PPC ads can help businesses see results more quickly by putting the site at the top of the search engine results page for relevant search terms. By appearing on the first page of the SERP, the business gains new visibility and searchers are more likely to find and click on the site. PPC ads not only generate more traffic to the site, but they can help to ensure that the leads which are getting are qualified. Those who are clicking on PPC ads are consumers who are searching for the topics that are most relevant to the products or services. This means that they are more likely to be interested in the brand and the products or services that are provided.

Email Marketing

Email marketing is one of the most successful digital marketing channels that have a huge Return on Investment (ROI). A lot of businesses use email marketing, and it as an excellent way for getting ROI. Companies can use branded emails to communicate with their target audience. Marketing emails are often used as a way to increase brand awareness, establish industry leadership, promote events, and get the word out about special promotions.

The content of the marketing emails will ultimately depend on the campaign goals. It is important to note that email marketing is mainly used not for generating new leads, but rather nurturing leads once they have shown interest. Marketing emails can also be used as part of the customer retention campaigns. Email marketing is also used to create a monthly newsletter to engage the leads or promote certain sales or discounts through email. However, it can also be used to support some of the other campaign tactics like content marketing and social media.

Chatbots

Chatbots - also known as conversational agents are software programs capable of doing automated chatting. Chatbots function by mimicking written texts or speech to interact and converse with the users. Chat bots can be highly beneficial in collecting customer insights, that can be stored, responded and applied in a suitable based on the past conversations. This can help a great deal in improving all the stages of marketing. According to Gartner.com, by 2020, almost 85% of the customer relationships will be amounted by AI. Further, the cost of chatbots has reduced radically due to Facebook's decision to allow third-party applications to develop chatbot on their Messenger platform.

Messaging is one of the most used features on smart phones and when it comes to chatbots, India has been on-par with global peers in terms of adoption. Companies large and small across industries from Banking, e-commerce, insurance, and entertainment have successfully implemented bots to assist users across platforms.

The year 2018 will put an end to dumb chatbots and will embrace smart AI and NLP powered chatbots which will allow users to have seamless communication. The lacks of smart chatbots have traditionally ruined the experience of users leading to conversation with little or no conclusion.

Chatbots can be incorporated with marketing strategies to maximise business in the following ways:

- Communicate with website visitors. Provide them with website information. Help them make a purchase.
- Integrating chatbots with messaging platforms saves a lot of time in email marketing.
- Sell the products using chatbots. 71% of people like personalised ads. Chat bots can persuade them better.
- Gain consumer insights to improve the quality of customer services.
- Increase proactive customer engagement, since it's a critical part of marketing.
- Build brand loyalty by offering customised services.
- Customise chatbot, based on geography to target appropriate audience.
- Upgrade the chatbot regularly and fix technical glitches.

In the near future, the chat bots shall govern our lives. Be it navigating, ordering food, booking tickets, making a purchase, or even consulting a psychiatrist; personalised chatbots seem to be everyone's friend and literally, an omnipresent entity.

Content Marketing

Content Marketing is a well-planned marketing tactic of generation and distribution of reliable, pertinent and valuable information, aimed to draw the interest of specified target audience with a motive of gaining profit. In other words, it is a method of grabbing the attention of target audience and resolving their queries about the product by providing relevant information. The belief here is that – over a period of time, the audience will build trust, rely on the content for directions, understand the uniqueness of the product, purchase the product, and develop brand loyalty.

Digital is the biggest platform from content marketing perspective in India due to lower restriction on brand promotion and the eco-system itself which is advertiser-led than being subscription-driven. Video has by far been the number-one preference for content marketing professionals and the same will remain in the future. The internet video traffic is expected to be over 80% of the consumer internet traffic by 2021, while content marketing will gain a whole new dimension in the marketing mix.

Content marketing strategy is the heart of every digital marketing campaign and is the major element that will remain constant in the marketplace. With good, high-quality and very relevant content, the website and other internet marketing real estate will generate considerable inbound traffic from highly targeted audiences all of which can be potential customers. Content includes text, image, videos, and other related materials people are looking for and are very interested in.

Content marketing, undoubtedly is gaining prominence every day. Contents govern the internet and marketing space. For instance, a recent study indicates about 77% of the internet users view blogs. Hence, it is not only what is delivered, but also how it is delivered that counts. In this regard, a lot of creative efforts must be put too, in order to make the content successful. Current trends suggest a good content must comprise of visuals. Hence, content marketing is in a strong phase of transformation by including new features such as infographics, podcasts, video contents etc.

Gen Z

Gen Z or the generation which was born around 2000 and who are in the age group of 11-18 years will slowly become part of the mainline society. The generation has grown up in a digital world where mobile and internet were synonymous. The generation likes to think and work practically and are no more in the look-out for a perfect world or a real-world scenario but believe in real world.

The generation is always online and active on social media platforms sharing content freely with a larger audience. The brands will have to be present and listen closely to the generation as they applaud or complain on platforms. The lower attention span time is yet another challenge brands will have to overcome while conversing with the generation. The brands will have to create a uniform experience across stores, websites, online communities wherein the Gen Z can walk and check out and make decisions. They are just beginning to enter the labour force, and will have increased buying power for some time.

Videos

Businesses create short 2 to 5-minute videos about specific topics and then upload the same to various video sharing websites like YouTube for distribution and exposure thus providing an excellent platform for marketing. Video consumption has been on a rise in India with the advent of Jio and low-cost smart phones. The year 2016-17 saw many national and international players entering the segment with their OTT services i.e. Netflix, Viu, Voot and Hotstar. Existing social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter have upped their ante against YouTube and other video incumbents.

The coming year will bring more live stories on Instagram, Facebook and YouTube. The trend of going live will further get a push with organizations setting up live studios similar to Selfie Stations for going live across platforms. In the race to supremacy, platforms will try to differentiate themselves with content type and communication leveraging their existing strategy. Globally, IP video traffic will be 82% of all consumer Internet traffic by 2021, up from 73% in 2016. Global IP video traffic will grow threefold from 2016 to 2021, a CAGR of 26%. Internet video traffic will grow fourfold from 2016 to 2021, a CAGR of 31%. Live Internet video will account for 13% of Internet video traffic by 2021. Live video will grow 15-fold from 2016 to 2021 as per CISCO VNI.

Augmented Reality

Augmented Reality has been growing at a blistering pace compared to its peer virtual reality. The addition of AR by Google-ARCore, Apple-ARKit and the like in their handsets have further strengthened the growth prospects with AR becoming a handy tool for content consumption and decimation. The recent adoption of AR by Amazon for its iOS apps will help it grow faster than most experts believe. The continuous up gradation of device performance, battery life and app-store eco-system will further push AR into mainstream.

The use of AR in industries apart from retail into real-estate, financial services and healthcare will further broaden the horizon and adoption. The broadened horizon for AR will surely push existing players across sectors to leverage the platform to deliver more, with better content for users to consume and embrace. As per DigiCapital Report, Mobile AR could become the primary driver of a \$108 billion VR/AR market by 2021.

Augmented Reality is an innovative technology that enhances the way we perceive the world by generating an additional dimension that layers information in form of sensory experiences. Augmented reality is gaining popularity because of its ability to add extra dimension to the reality in terms of sounds and visuals. In fact, giants like Google have invested in Google Glass – that has developed gadgets integrated with augmented reality. This means, a new ‘dimension’ itself has been created for marketing domain. Augmented Reality itself has become a medium, which has opened doors for several marketing strategies. AR marketing is going to dominate the future arena. According to Vibrant Media, nearly 70% of the media planners and buyers seek to include AR ads into their digital marketing campaigns due to increasing demand for customer engagement. Some of the major prospects in AR marketing are listed below.

- Content Marketing – There is lot of opportunity in content development in AR, as you can upgrade or customise your existing content with the use of filters and visual stickers to suit the medium.
- Advertising – As AR is a new medium by itself, you can integrate “try before you buy” tactic in ad-campaigns. Due to the depth in interaction and immersion that AR provides, advertising can be done very differently. Imagine selling apparels, where the users can actually ‘try it on’ before they actually buy it. This also reduces the product return rate.

- App Development – If you can develop an app that incorporates AR, then your customers can engage with your brand more deeply and directly. Apps have the ability to engage the users to constantly. A good example for AR app is Pokémon Go, which has proved its success by seeing more than 100 million downloads and grossing revenue of USD 268 million within a year of its launch.

Virtual Reality

In simple terms, Virtual Reality (VR) can be described as the latest digital technology that provides the users with an experience of being in another dimension altogether with the help of computer based simulation. Also referred to as ‘immersive reality’, VR has had a long term association with the gaming industry. The demand for VR in marketing is increasing every day due to its ability to get the audience closer and personal with specific products. Although VR was an out-of-reach technology initially, it is soon expected to lead the world in the near future.

According to Digital Marketing Institute, 75% of the major global brands have already incorporated VR into their marketing strategy, proving it to be a powerful tool for marketing. Though VR was initially used in the gaming sector, the latest development in digital technology has enabled it to be successfully implemented in leading sectors such as Education, Training, Healthcare, Tourism, Automotive etc. This also suggests, new avenues have been created for Advertising and Marketing in the respective fields, thanks to the advent of Virtual Reality.

VR provides an exclusive opportunity for marketers to literally ‘immerse’ the audience into their product. However, if the ad quality is not up to the mark, then it not only impacts the audience with a negative impression (which is far more effective), but also sabotages their VR experience altogether. Hence, an excessive amount of creativity must be applied in advertising and marketing strategy.

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence has been making progress in leaps and bounds in IoT, Chatbots, self-driving cars. The impact of AI will be seen in a wide variety of products and services from content marketing to social media and performance marketing.

Digital Marketing for brands with Artificial Intelligence can be ground breaking. The data crunched in terms of customer searches, buying behaviour and interest can be used to customize content better and design ads for the target audience. Each time a user engages online, a new data point is created which can be leveraged for providing personalized services. Businesses will start incorporating AI into their daily processes such as assisting customers in purchase decisions, answering chats, and deliver personalized web experience.

Hyperlocal

Google being the dominant search engine in the market today, took its first step towards localization with My Business services. Over the years, competition and players alike have invested in localization of their search and services to personalize it to the consumer needs. The localization has even made companies big and small invest in local SEO in their marketing arsenal.

The inclusion of social media has taken hyperlocal a step further with local business pages and events providing easy access of users split in the geography and a much specific target audience. In the coming days, localization of search will no more be restricted to brands and bigger chains. Each and every organization in the eco-system will have to be present when users look for information be it in the form of location, direction, contact nos. Digital platform will force each and every offline activity to be available in search to be relevant in the business place.

Mobile apps

Mobile apps refer to the software applications which are exclusively developed to be used on smart phones and tablets. In the world’s leading app store, Google Play Store has about 2.8 million apps available, followed by 2.2 million in Apple’s App Store. These numbers are increasing every day, indicating the popularity of mobile apps.

According to Statista, by 2020, it is estimated that mobile apps will contribute to global revenue of USD 189 billion through in-app advertising. This hints at the highly promising scope of mobile app marketing. However, the competition is stern too. With more and more companies investing in mobile app marketing, one needs to come up with innovative strategies to be successful in their ventures. The rapidly growing

numbers of mobile apps has already led to a booming mobile developer population. In fact, there are innovative strategies such as the 'hybrid monetization model' being developed, in order to maximise the revenue through in-app advertisements and purchases. Interestingly, mobile-app consumers' rate is progressing rapidly than the mobile app developers. It is estimated that by the end of 2018, there will be 369.01 million internet users, among which majority of them are mobile internet users. By 2022, a whopping number of 442.5 million smart phones will be sold in India. Thus, there is a huge demand for mobile app development in India.

Key Challenges of Digital Marketing:

Digital marketing is always going to be a changing industry because the online world is changing rapidly. There is also a change in the way people interact online, the software they use, the devices they use, and more. Staying on top of all these changes is always going to be a challenge. The following are the challenges faced by digital marketers today.

User Experience and Design

One of the biggest challenges of digital marketing is the need to have unique and better user experience. Along with the technical and platform growth, the need to have competitive designs to give a great user experience for the consumer has risen phenomenally. A traveller's user experience is different to that of an online shopper – understanding each of such end user's mindset while laying down the design of application is the most challenging task.

Generating Quality Traffic and Leads

Generating quality traffic and leads is one of the top marketing challenges digital marketers are facing. They are fighting with producing enough demand for their content. As there are lots of platforms to publish and promote the content, it's hard to identify which platforms they should use.

Targeting Audience

In a country like ours, understanding the end users of the channel over which digital marketers work, can help combat the challenges of digital marketing in India. Regional segmentation of audience, languages they speak and the cultural differences can pose difficulties but devising strategies for unique segments and promoting content for the tastes of the audience is definitely achievable. The digital marketers should know the voice of the customer to baseline their marketing strategies.

Optimizing Marketing Budgets and ROI

Measuring the ROI (Return on Investment) of marketing activities is another challenging task and it's getting more challenging by every passing year. Working with a limited budget could be the pain for marketers to work effectively as well as getting their marketing goals. Especially for small businesses that aren't working with a planned marketing budget. Every measure and strategy in the digital marketing space is now measurable. Marketers must gauge their marketing efforts and see if they are successfully converting them as per organizational goals so that the business has the projected ROI for its spend.

Optimizing the Mobile Experience

With the audience switching to handheld devices and seeking faster page loads with better user experience, digital marketing teams have to gear up to be suggestive of methodologies to retain such users for the customer. One ought to remember that the expectations keep varying for each business but the constant traffic from mobile users is definitely increasing.

Updates on Trends

The digital marketing trends are evolving each day and it becomes imperative for every company catering to fulfilling digital marketing needs for their customers to stay updated on them. There are more tools, complex social media strategies and technology advancements that are to be taken into account and to stay updated.

Digital Marketing and its impact on Consumer Perception:

Some of the major implications of digital marketing on the consumer perception are as follows:

Brand Creation

Digital marketing has the potential to create a brand. That would mean all aspects of it, whether it is awareness, the values it stands for, the loyalty and overall image. Depending on how the digital media is used one can actually create a very powerful brand, which has a high degree of recall in the minds of the consumers. That is how the consumer perception is impacted at the first level. It then shifts to the way the brand is positioned through what its social media platforms share or how the messages to the consumers are passed on. All consumers currently are more tech-savvy than they have been in the past decades. Their connection to the brand comes from their online interaction. And that drives their perception. A brand that focuses on making sure that its social media and digital platforms share messages which resonate with the consumers is what creates the right perception.

Business Vision

Consumers are always keen to know what the organization's vision is or how its business strategy will unfold. This is part of the overall brand image and linked to their belief in the organization, as well as its products or services. Digital marketing is an excellent tool to share the business vision, product launches, new growth plans, and the future trajectory with the consumers. It allows the consumers to become a part of the organization in a virtual manner, and the consumer perceives himself or herself to be associated with the business. In some form, the consumer feels a part of the overall success of the organization.

Communication

When the digital media is effectively used for marketing, the marketers send the message out about the quality of their communication. Marketers can also demonstrate how they are effectively using technology to connect with those who matter – the consumers and end users. Or even potential clients. Consumers see the organization as one which is future-focused and also serious about reaching out to its clients, when they see the digital marketing approach. They become aware of the efforts and investment the businesses are putting in. They realize that the organization will go an extra mile to get the right messages across to them.

Information sharing and Complaint Resolution

When a consumer decides to purchase the product or even review the benefits of the service, he or she starts checking all the business pages on the internet, the social media channels, the official website, reviewer sites and even any community groups which might have feedback. Some consumers might even register a query or complaint through the digital media platforms. If the businesses are active on that front, they will be able to manage it in a timely manner and ensure that the consumer perceives them as efficient as well as an organization that values its clients. The perception about the consumer service levels are impacted significantly by this. There are many instances of large as well as small organizations of having used this approach to resolve consumer issues, and effectively at that.

Customer Engagement

Anything that involves, excites and engages customers can be done better with the digital media, because it allows to interact with the consumer such as contest, a quiz, a trial or a pilot test of a new service. And customers love that kind of engagement. It gives them opportunity to try out something new and a chance to win or gain something from that exchange. Existing and potential consumers can see the kind of thought process that goes behind such an initiative and that adds to their perception of the brand or organization's image.

That is the power of digital marketing in terms of the perception it creates in the minds of consumers. The consumers can be located in any part of the world. They can belong to any gender, colour, age or income bracket. Digital marketing and how it is used, can make an impact on any individual's mind through the way it tells the story of the organization. Consumer perception is a fickle thing – if there is a consistent digital marketing strategy, it can ensure that the right perception is created and retained.

Conclusion

The year 2019 will be about better customer experience with personalization, automation and AI-powered technology. To stay ahead of the curve and increase conversions in the coming year, marketers need to get better at producing custom, conversational content – particularly audio and video content – to share with the

better-targeted audience. As 2019 approaches, the digital marketing landscape that encompasses SEO, social media, PPC, content marketing and more is witnessing a dramatic shift. There are many new digital marketing trends and strategies that are evolving in the current high-tech, Internet-connected era and the businesses now need to use them to succeed in their efforts because what worked for the last year may not work this year.

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